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The Fossilized Pronunciation of the /3:/ Sound in the Speech of Intermediate Tunisian English Students: Problem, Reasons and Suggested Solution

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ABSTRACT

Fossilization is a universal phenomenon that has attracted the attention of teachers and researchers alike. In this regard, the aim of this study is to investigate a supposedly fossilized feature in Tunisian learners' performance, namely the pronunciation of the /3:/ sound among Intermediate Tunisian English Students (ITES). It tries to show whether ITES pronounce it correctly or whether it is rather often replaced by another phoneme. The study also tries to show the reasons behind fossilization. It is conjectured that L1 interference, lack of exposure to L2 input, and the absence of pronunciation teaching methods are the main factors behind this fossilized pronunciation. Finally, the study tries to apply the audio-articulation method to remedy for this type of fossilization. This method contains many drills that can help learners articulate better, and consequently produce more intelligible sounds.

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1. Introduction

One of the important differences between the processes of acquiring a first language (L1) and learning a second language (L2) is the phenomenon of fossilization, which occurs during L2 acquisition (Selinker 1972, Selinker & Lamendella 1978, Han 2004, 2011, 2013). While acquiring L1, the child as a rule achieves native like competence. Learners, on the other hand, generally commit errors in learning the L2, and therefore fail to achieve native-like competence due to the persistence of such errors. Obviously these errors can be temporary, and may disappear over time. Alternatively, they can be permanent, thus resisting correction. When we talk about persistent errors, we talk about the phenomenon of fossilization. Fossilization occurs when non-target rules become fixed in the learner's interlanguage. Against this background, the present study investigates the fossilized pronunciation of the /ʒ:/ sound in the performance of ITES. It tries to show how this sound is often replaced by other phonemes. It also looks into some possible reasons that might lead to this type of fossilization. The study concludes with a suggestion to apply the audio-articulation method, which can be a possible cure for this fossilized sound.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The concept 'Interlanguage'

The term Interlanguage (IL) was introduced by Larry Selinker in 1972. It is defined by him in the following terms: "A separate linguistic system based on the observable output which results from a learner's attempted production of a TL form" (1972: 35) It is a language system produced by learners that neither belongs to the native language (NL) nor to the target language (TL), although it shares rules with both.

Selinker argues that the overwhelming majority of learners (perhaps as many as 95%) never manage to reach native-like fluency. All they can reach, he maintains, is 'attempted learning' or 'attempted meaningful performance', referring to "the situation where an 'adult' attempts to express meanings, which he may already have, in a language which he is in the process of learning" (1972:32)

As opposed to this overwhelming majority, the small minority (averaging 5%) is actually able to reach the top, as it were, and to become very close to NS competence. Selinker refers to this process as 'successful learning'. However, it is to be noted that since this small group constitutes the exception rather than the rule, they cannot possibly be the real subject of investigation; as Selinker put it: "This 5% go through very different psycholinguistic processes than do most second language learners and these successful learners may be safely ignored – in a counterfactual sense – for the purposes of establishing the constructs which point to the psychologically relevant data pertinent to most second language learners" (1972: 34). Furthermore, in contradistinction to Lenneberg's concept of 'latent biological structure' (1967), Selinker hypothesized a 'latent psychological structure', which he argues to be an innate mechanism in the brain, and comprised five central processes: language transfer, transfer of training, overgeneralization, learning strategies, and communication strategies.

Nemser (1969) used the term "Approximative System" to refer to IL. He defined this system as "the deviant linguistic system actually employed by the learner attempting to utilize the target language" (p.2). According to Nemser (1969), the Approximate System varies in character in accordance with proficiency level, learning

experience, communication function, personal learning characteristics etc. Corder (1971) also used the phrases ‘*Idiosyncratic Dialect*’, ‘*Transitional Competence*’ and ‘*Transitional Dialect*’ to refer to almost the same concept. It has to be noted, however, that the term ‘interlanguage’ has outlived the other appellations, and is now the one that is overwhelmingly used in the second language acquisition (SLA) literature.

Figure 1: Transitional Dialects

(Corder, 1971, P.151)

As the figure shows, the interlanguage is a continuum between the first language and the target language. It is a unique system independent from the first language and the TL. At the same time, however, it shares some rules both with the NL and the TL; in this way, Corder reasons, it is eligible to be called ‘dialect’: “Two languages which share some rules of grammar are dialects” (1981: 14). One premise Corder bases his argument on is the fact that “any spontaneous speech intended by the speaker to communicate is meaningful, in the sense that it is systematic, regular, and consequently is, in principle, describable in terms of a set of rules, i.e. it has a grammar” (1981: 14).

2.2 Fossilization

As pointed out earlier, the term fossilization was introduced by Larry Selinker in 1972. He defined it then in the following words: “Fossilizable linguistic phenomena are linguistic items, rules and subsystems which speakers of a particular NL will tend to keep in their IL relative to a particular TL, no matter what the age of the

learner or amount of explanation and instruction he receives in the TL” (1972: 36). Han (2013: 133) defines it as “an interlanguage-unique phenomenon in which a semi-developed linguistic form or construction shows permanent resistance to environmental influence and thus fails to progress towards the target”. The *Encyclopedic Dictionary of Applied Linguistics* defines fossilization as:

The phenomenon whereby linguistic items (particularly erroneous ones) become permanent in a learner’s Interlanguage. The term was used by Selinker (1972) in relation to the processes of ‘levelling’ (lack of forward movement) or ‘regression’ (‘backsliding’ where a learner’s language reverts to an earlier stage). Fossilization may occur in relation to any linguistic level, ‘foreign accent’ being the result of one form of fossilization. (p.135)

So fossilization refers to the stagnation in a learner’s IL. It is the cessation of learning and the lack of progression in the learning process. In the *Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics*, fossilization is described as “the stabilization of a level of achievement in the use of a linguistic form which falls short of the norms of the target language. No further learning takes place, and the form becomes a fossilized error in the usage of the learner, part of the learner’s interlanguage” (p.197). Fossilization is a stage in the acquisition of a second language or a foreign language. It is characterized by the stabilization of target language norms till it becomes permanent. The *Longman dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics* defines fossilization as:

...a process (in second language learning) which sometimes occurs in which incorrect linguistic features become a permanent part of the way a person speaks or writes a language.

Aspects of pronunciation, vocabulary usage, and grammar may become fixed or fossilized in second language learning. Fossilized features of pronunciation contribute to a person's foreign accent.

These definitions suggest that fossilization involves many areas such as grammar, lexis, and pronunciation. It is the end of learning in the IL of learners. The definitions also clarify the major characteristics of IL.

2.2.1 Temporary and permanent fossilization

Selinker (1972) makes the distinction between two types of fossilization, temporary fossilization and permanent fossilization. This is shown in the following figure:

Figure 2: Temporary Fossilization and Permanent Fossilization

(Wei, 2008, p.131)

Temporary fossilization is a momentary habit that disappears overtime but permanent fossilization does not disappear even after correction and formal instruction.

2.2.2 Grammatical Fossilization

A considerable amount of second language acquisition research has focused on grammatical fossilization. Han and Selinker (1999) conducted a study on grammatical fossilization. They examined the interlanguage of Siri, a female from Thailand. The findings showed that Siri omitted the subject from sentences when it was necessary. She also used "to have" when the structure needed was "there be." Han and Selinker (1999) argued that after a

pedagogical treatment, Siri kept omitting the subject. Fauziati (2011) studied errors of fossilization made by Indonesian students. The results of the study indicated that the grammatical errors of Indonesian students can be categorized into: verb to be, bound morpheme, sentences structure, noun uses as a verb, prepositions and pronouns. According to Fauziati, some errors were destabilized, some were fluctuating and others were stabilized (p.35).

Butler-Tanaka (2000) also conducted a study on grammatical fossilization of Japanese adult learners of English. The findings showed that there were a number of grammatical errors including articles, prepositions, inappropriate verb choice, auxiliary verbs and modal verbs. The researcher claimed that the consciousness-raising approach can be used to avoid fossilization. Similarly, Nazadze (2012) studied fossilized grammatical errors committed by Georgian students of English. The results showed that there are different types of errors, namely word order, verb tenses and articles. It is argued that, in order to overcome this, comparison drills can be the suitable way to overcome fossilization.

In the same vein of research, Veronica Diane de Wit (2007) carried out a study on the fossilization of an adult learner. He investigated the oral performance of an adult learner over a period of nine months. The outcome of the study showed that the learner made a number of fossilized errors in four areas, basically morphology, syntax, semantics and vocabulary. The result of the study also showed that fossilization is the result of L1, input and learning materials.

Therefore, a substantial number of studies have been carried out to study the fossilized grammatical errors committed by Second language learners. It seems to be a general agreement on the factors behind

grammatical fossilization which include L1, input and strategies of learning. However; other trend of literature concentrated on studying the fossilized phonetic errors.

2.2.3 Phonetic Fossilization

Few studies examined phonetic fossilization. Kahraman (2012) studied the fossilized pronunciation of the vowel phoneme /æ/ and the possible ways to overcome this fossilization. According to the study, most Turkish learners of English, articulate /æ/ vowel phoneme as /e/. Kahraman proposed the audio-articulation method to remedy fossilization. Demirezen (2005) studied the /ɔ/ and /ow/ sounds of Turkish students of the English language. He also studied the fossilized pronunciation of the /v/ and /w/ sounds. Demirezen used the audio-articulation method to solve the problem.

Additionally, Nilawati (2008) conducted a study on fossilized phonetic errors. The participants were eight students from the English Department of the Faculty of Letter ANDALAS University. Based on the results, there are four types of fossilized phonetic errors, namely consonant omission, error of consonant selection, error of vowel selection and diphthong selection. These errors are the result of three causes: phonological interference from mother tongue, the complexity of English and insufficient input and corrective feedback.

In the Tunisian context, it seems that no study has been done to investigate the phonetic fossilization of Intermediate Tunisian English students. Therefore, the present study tries to fill a gap in this area through the investigation the fossilized pronunciation of the /ɜ:/ sound in a group of university students of English. The study spanned a period of three months. It also tries to show what the target phonemes were replaced by, and the factors behind this

fossilized pronunciation. Finally, the study proposes the audio-articulation method as a solution to overcome this problem.

3. Methodology

The participants of the study were 10 students from the Department of English at the Faculty of Arts & Humanities of Kairouan, Tunisia. They were enrolled in second year English at the time of the experiment. Their ages vary between 21 and 25. They were two males and eight females. The phonetics component at this faculty (as in other English departments across the country) is dealt with in the first and second years. Students go through some aspects pertaining to place and manner of articulation, strong and weak forms, as well as some aspects of intonation and supra-segmental features in general.

The experiment in the present study has two phases in it: time one and time two. The researchers recorded data on time one and then on time two. The aim was to know the pronunciation of the /ɜ:/ sound. We asked the students to pronounce some words containing the sound /ɜ:/. After one year period, the subjects were asked to pronounce the same words. The main goal was to see whether they pronounce the sound /ɜ:/ correctly or they rather tend to replace it with other sounds. The researchers used the program called 'audacity' to record the data and the EXCEL program for calculations.

4. Results and Discussion

The results of the study show that 3 students pronounced the /ɜ:/ sound correctly. However, 7 students mispronounced the /ɜ:/ sound and they replaced it with the /ɔ:/ sound. The /ɜ:/ sound appeared 5 times and the /ɔ:/ sound 25 times, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 3: The frequency of /ɜ:/ and /ɔ:/ sounds on Time-1

After one-year period, little development was detected in the pronunciation of the students. They kept using the /ɔ:/ sound instead of the /3:/ sound. The /ɔ:/ sound was pronounced 20 times and the /3:/ sound 10 times, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 4: The frequency of /3:/ and /ɔ:/ sounds on Time-2

The students' pronunciation of this sound thus appears to be fossilized. In this respect, Tarone (1994) has noted that the "central characteristic of any IL is that it fossilizes" (p.747). Their interlanguage is also preamble in the sense that they are open to influence from the native language or the first language (Adjemian 1976). Yip (1995) has also emphasized "the susceptibility of IL to infiltration by first language and target language rules or forms" (p. 12).

There are many factors that affect students' interlanguage. The first language (in this case Arabic) can influence the pronunciation of ITES. Besides, the French sound /ɔ:/ is pronounced in the place of the English /3:/sound. According to Han (2009), the L1 "...provides the initial building materials to be gradually blended with

material taken from the Target Language" (p.137). The Arabic or French pronunciations thus interfere into the acquisition of the English pronunciation. Lack of exposure to L2 input can be another factor of fossilization. As a matter of fact, These students learn English only through formal instruction and they do not use English outside the classroom. The level of absenteeism in oral language classes is also very high, unfortunately. So the lack of practice in spoken English may well lead them to this type of fossilization. The absence of pronunciation teaching methods is another factor that can lead to fossilization. Therefore, classroom curriculum should give more importance to pronunciation and courses in phonetics and phonology.

5. Application of the Audio-Articulation Method

5.1 The Audio-Articulation Method

The Audio-Articulation Method was developed by Mehmet Demirezen (2003, 2004) as a "fossilized mistake breaker" (as cited in Kahraman, 2013, p.269). This method starts with a motivation warm up, which takes some minutes. Then it extends to a review of previous topic and the presentation, practice and production of the language to be taught.

5.2 Preparing of a Corpus

According to the principles of the audio-articulation method, the researcher prepares a corpus of 80 to 100 words, having to do with this fossilized problem-causing phoneme, then develops all his/her exercises from this corpus. In this research, the words and the phonetic transcription cited in the corpus were taken from *Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary* 7th edition. The researchers used the words from the corpus and developed other drilling techniques like

minimal pairs contrast, chain drills, substitutions drills, repetition drills, inflectional drills, replacement drills, restatement drills, substitution drills, contradiction drills, transformation drills, integration drills, rejoinder drills, restoration drills, question-answer drills, language games, and many other creative types.

Table1: Corpus

Accord /æk ɔ:d/ /æk ɔ:rd/ ¹	Inform /infɔ:m/ /infɔ:rm/
Asserted / əs3:tid/ /əs3:rtid/	Infirm /inf3:m/ /inf3:rm/
Assorted /əsɔ:tid/ / əsɔ:rtid/	Lawn /lɔ:n/
Auburn /ɔ:bən/ /ɔ:bərn/	Learn /lɜ:n/ /l3:rn/
Auk /ɔ:k/	Mortal /mɔ:tl/ /mɔ:rtl/
Awe /ɔ: /	Myrth /m3:tl/ /m3:rtl/
Awl /ɔ: l/	Norse /nɔ:s/ /nɔ:rs/
Awning /ɔ:inŋ/	Nurse /nɜ:s/ /n3:rs/
Balk /bɔ:lk/	Orgy /ɔ:dʒi/ /ɔ:rdʒi/
Baulk /b ɔ:k/ /bɔ:lk/	Urge /3:dʒ/ /3:rdʒ/
Bawd /bɔ:d/	Pearl /p3:l/ /p3:rl/
Blackboard /blækbɔ:d/ / blækbɔ:rd/	Purl /p3:l/ /p3:rl/
Boar / bɔ:(r)/	Pawn /pɔ:n/
Board /bɔ:d/ / bɔ:rd/	Pore /pɔ:(r)/
Bore /b ɔ:(r)/	Pert /p3:t/ /p3:rt/
bird /b3:d/ /b3:rd/	Purn /p3:n/ /p3:rn/
blackbird /blækb3:d/ / blækb3:rd/	Port /pɔ:t/ /pɔ:rt/
bur /b3:(r)/	Portion /pɔ:ʃn/ /pɔ:rʃn/
burn /b3:n/ / b3:rn/	Persian /p3:ʃn/ /
called /kɔ:ld/	Record /rekɔ:d/ /rekɔ:rd/
caller / k ɔ:lə/ /kɔ:lər/	Short /ʃɔ:t/ /ʃɔ:rt/
calling /kɔ:liŋ/	Shirt /ʃ3:t/ /ʃ3:rt/
caught /kɔ:t/	Soar /sɔ:(r)/
caul / kɔ:l/	Sir /s3:(r)/
caw /kɔ:/	Sort /sɔ:t/ /sɔ:rt/
conform /kɔnf ɔ:m/ /kɔnf ɔ:rm/	Spawn /spɔ:n/
consort / k ɔns ɔ:t/ / k ɔns ɔ:rt/	Sport /spɔ:t/ /spɔ:rt/
cord / k ɔ:d/ / k ɔ:rd/	Spurn /sp3:n/ /sp3:rn/
core /kɔ:(r)/	Spurt /spu3:t/ /spu3:rt/
cork / k ɔ:k/ / kɔ:rk/	Store /stɔ:(r)/
corse / kɔ:s/ / kɔ:rs/	Stir /st3:(r)/
curl /k3:l/ /k3:rl/	Talk /tɔ:(r)/
Course / kɔ:s/ / kɔ:rs/	Torn /tɔ:n/ /tɔ:rn/
Curler /k3:lə/ /k3:lər/	Turk /t3:k/ /t3:rk/
Curt / k3:t/ /k3:rt/	Tern /t3:n/ /t3:rn/
Curd / k3:d/ /k3:rd/	Vortex /vɔ:teks/
Confirm /kɔnf3:m/ /kɔnf3:rm/	Vertex /v3:teks/ /v3:rteks/
Curse /k3:s/ /k3:rs/	Walk /wɔ:k/
Exhort /igzɔ:t/ / igzɔ:rt/	Work /w3:k/ /w3:rk/
Fall /fɔ:l/	Walker /wɔ:kə(r)/
Furl /f3:l/ /f3:rl/	Worker /w3:kə/ /w3:kər/
Faun /f ɔ:n/	Wall /wɔ:l/
Fern /f3:n/ / f3:rn/	Whorl /w3:l/ /w3:rl/
For /fɔ:(r)/ /fɔ:r/	World /w3:d/ /w3:rd/

Fur /f3:(r)/	Ward /wɔ:d/ /wɔ:rd/
Forced / fɔ:st/ /fɔ:rst/	Warm /wɔ:m/ /wɔ:rm/
First /f3:st/ /f3:rst/	Worm /w3:m/ /w3:rm/
Form /fɔ:m/ /fɔ:rm/	War /wɔ:(r) /
Firm /f3:m/ /f3:rm/	Whirr /w3:(r)/
Forth /f ɔ: θ/ / f ɔ:rθ/	Warship /wɔ:ʃip/ /wɔ:rʃip/
Furth /f3:θ/ / f3:rθ/	Worship /w3:ʃip/ /w3:rʃip/
Four /fɔ:(r) /	Wart /wɔ:t/ /wɔ:rt/
Furze /f3:z/ / f3:rz/	Wert /w3:t/ /w3:rt/
Fourth /f ɔ:θ/ / f ɔ:rθ/	Yawn /jɔ:n/
Firth /f3: θ/ / f3:rθ/	Yearn /j3:n/ /j3:rn/
Gall /gɔ:l/	Your /jɔ:(r)/
Girl /g3:l/ /g3:rl/	Year /jie(r)/ /j3:r/
Hurl /h3:l/ /h3:rl/	
Hoarse /hɔ:s/ /hɔ:rs/	
Hearse /h3:s/ /h3:rs/	
Hall /hɔ:l/	

[The first transcription is British and the second is American. Some words have the same American and British transcriptions .That is why we used only one transcription.]

Table 2: Minimal Pairs

²	/ɔ: /	/3:/
Accord /ækɔ:rd/		Occurred /æk3:rid/
Assorted /əsɔ:rtid/		Asserted /əs3:rtid/
Auburn /ɔ:bərn/		Urban /3:rβən/
Auk /ɔ:k/		Irk /3:rk/
Awe /ɔ: /		Ugh /3:/
Awl /ɔ:l/		Earl /3:rl/
Awning /ɔ:inŋ/		Earning /3:rniŋ/
Balk /bɔ:lk/		Burke /b3:rk/
Bawd /bɔ:d/		Bird /b3:rd/
Called /kɔ:ld/		Curled /k3:rlid/
Caught /kɔ:t/		Curt /k3:rt/
caw /kɔ:/		Curd /k3:rd/
conform /kɔnfɔ:rm/		Confirm /kɔnf3:rm/
Corse /kɔ:rs/		Curse /k3:rs/
Course /kɔ:rs/		Curse /k3:rs/
Fall /fɔ:l/		Furl / f3:rl/
For /fɔ:r/		Fur /f3:(r)/
Forced /fɔ:rst/		First /f3:rst/
Form /fɔ:rm/		Firm /f3:rm/
Gall /gɔ:l/		Girl /g3:rl/
Hall /hɔ:l/		Hurl /h3:rl/
Hoarse /hɔ:rs/		Hearse /h3:rs/
Inform /infɔ:rm/		Infirm /inf3:rm/

[The American transcription is used.]

Practicing the topic:

The /3:/ sound is replaced by the /ɔ: / sound. The researcher used the tongue twisters to solve the pronunciation problem. Students repeated the tongue twisters one by one or in groups.

Tongue Twisters:

-A Persian person purchased a perfect purple purse on purpose.

-A poor pauper paused on purpose to pawn a porpoise.

-Urgent detergent.

Recognition exercise

The following exercise was also made use of in the treatment:

Example 1:

The researcher: Dear colleagues, I am going to give you some words now, if you hear the sound /ɔ:/ say one, if you hear the /ɜ:/ sound, you say two. Here is an example:

Researcher: student1, which sound do you hear in the word “board”?

Student1: one.

R: Good. Thank you.S2, you tell me, which sound we hear in the word “bird”.

S2: two.

R: very good, S2.S3, which sound is heard in the word “burn”?

S3: two.

R: well done, S3, thank you.

Example2:

Researcher: Dear friend, now I am going to give you two words. If you hear the sound /ɔ:/ you say one, if you hear the sound /ɜ:/, you say two. Here is an example:

R: Student4, which sound do you hear in the word “caught” and “curl”.

S4: one and two.

R: correct, thank you S4.S5, “curl/call”.

S5: two-one.

R: very good, S5.S6 “cords/curds”.

S6: one-two!

R: well done, thank you.

Example 3:

R: now I am going to give you three words. If you hear /ɔ:/ sound you say one, or if you hear the sound /ɜ:/, you say two. Here an example:

S7 you tell me, which sound do you hear in the words “call, bird, yawn.”

S7: one-two-one.

R: very good S7.S8 “Sir, warm, work.”

S8: two-one-two.

R: well done

Giving the rule

/ɔ:/ is long mid back rounded vowel, as in the following words, fall, walk, gall, inform...

/ɜ:/ is long mid central spread vowel, as in the following items, word, world, bird, first...

Figure 5: The following figure shows the articulation of the two sounds: (Ann Baker, 1991 p43)

Doing more exercises:

1-Sentences with contextual clues:

-She bought a **short** shirt.

-He **walks** to his **work**.

-**You** celebrated your first **year** of marriage.

-The **worm** lives in a **warm** atmosphere.

-He **hurls** the **hall**.

-She **forced** him to be the **first** candidate.

2-Provide the phonetic transcription of the following minimal pairs:

Bought/bert

Boar/bur

Caul/curl

Cawed/curd

Fall/furl

Horn/herne

Or/err

Giving Assignments

The researcher can give the following tasks as homework.

1- Repeat all the exercises at home.

2- Prepare 5 minimal pairs.

- 3- Prepare 3 sentences with contextual clues.
- 4- Prepare 3 tongue twisters.
- 5- Write a dialogue including /ɔ:/ and /ɜ:/ vowel phonemes.
- 6- Write a paragraph (in 200 words) by using the words given in the corpus.

Based on the findings of the present study, the audio-articulation model can be used to remedy phonetic fossilization. It integrates pronunciation practice into oral communication. According to Demirezen (2005), this model serves many functions. It promotes oral fluency and productive competence (p.82). It is recommended, therefore, that the curriculum of pronunciation should include this method. It will enrich the language teaching through the use of explicit phonetic exercises. It will also develop the teaching of pedagogy.

6. Conclusion

Pronunciation is a motor skill. It is necessary to find out the errors that learners face and to study them. The nature of errors can help L2 teachers and learners understand the process of learning and to find out the suitable solutions to overcome the problem. The ITES face the problem of Fossilization and the present study attempted to tackle this issue. The results showed how the /ɜ:/ sound is replaced by the /ɔ:/ sound and how the phenomenon becomes fossilization in the speech of ITES. After the investigation, the researcher suggests that the Audio-articulation method can be used to handle such fossilized errors because the phonetic fossilization can harm the communicative competence of the learners. The study has its limitations also but it surely can be guiding light for future endeavors in this area. The limited number of students for data, their geographical location, gender etc are the limitations and more research is needed in

this regard focusing on each aspect of this. Even the other fossilized sounds can also be the area for investigation. To conclude, the pronunciation curriculum, in Tunisia, should give importance to the audio-articulation method.

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References

- Baker, A.** (1991). *Ship or Sheep: An Intermediate Pronunciation Course*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Corder, S.P.** (1971). Idiosyncratic Dialect and Error Analysis. *IRAL* 9, 2, 147-160.
- Crystal, D.** (ed.). (2008). *A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics* (6th edn). Hong Kong: Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
- Demirezen, M.** (2005). The / ɔ/ and /ow/ Contrast: Curing a Fossilized Pronunciation Error of Turkish Teacher Trainees of English language. *Journal of Arts and Sciences* 3, 71-84.
- Fauziati, E.** (2011). Interlanguage and Error Fossilization: A Study of Indonesian Students Learning English as a Foreign Language. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics* 1, 1, 23-38.
- Han, Z. & Larry, S.** (1999). Error Resistance: Towards an Empirical Pedagogy. *Language Teaching Research* 3, 3, 248-275.
- Han, Z.** (2009). Interlanguage and Fossilization: Towards an Analytic Model. In V. Cook & L. Wei (Eds.), *Contemporary Applied Linguistics*. London: Continuum.
- Johnson, K. & Johnson, H.** (1998). *Encyclopedic Dictionary of Applied Linguistics*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Kahraman, A** (2012). Defossilization of /æ/ Phoneme Pronunciation of Non-native EFL Teachers. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research* 3, 3, 379-385.

Kahraman, A. (2013). EFL Teachers' Fossilized Pronunciation Problem of Dark /l/ and the Solution. *Dumlupinar Universitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi* 35,269-279.

Nilawati, N. (2008). *The Fossilized Phonetic Errors of the English Department Students of ANDALAS University : An Interlanguage Study*. M.A.Thesis. English Department-Faculty of Letters ANDALAS University.

Nemser, W. (1971). Approximative Systems of Foreign Language Learners. *International Review of Applied Linguistics* 9,115-124.

Nozadze, A. (2012). Dealing with Fossilized Errors while Teaching Grammar. *Journal of Education* 1, 1, 41-46.

Richards, J., Platt, J. & Platt, H. (eds). (1992). *Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics* (2nd edn). Essex: Longman.

Selinker, L. (1972). Interlanguage. *International Review of Applied Linguistics in Language Teaching* 10, 3,209-231.

Tanaka, P. B. (2000). *Fossilization: A Chronic Condition or is Consciousness-Raising the Cure?* (Published MA dissertation), Birmingham University.

Tarone, E. (2006). Interlanguage. *Elsevier Ltd* 4,747-752.

Wei, X. (2008). Implication of IL Fossilization in Second Language Acquisition. *English Language Teaching* 1, 1, 127-131.

Appendix1:

Corpus: 30 words

Work, worm, wormed, worming, word, worded, wording, world, worker, worked, working, worship, whorl, wert, tourney, occur, curse, curt, nurse, hearse, turk, turkey, surd, curse, purple, urban, purpose, person, burn, furze.